

STUDIES IN ENZYMES AMYLASE FROM KASERU (*SCIRPUS GROSSUS*, LINN.)

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The amylase from Kaseru has an optimum p_n between 5·8 and 6·2 and optimum temperature between 50 and 55 using buffers according to Clark and Lubbs.

This investigation relates to the presence of amylase in the tuberous root of the herb Kaseru (*Scirpus grossus*, Linn, N.O. *cyperaceæ*) its extraction and study of optimum temperature and p_n . The amylase isolated has an optimum p_n between 5·8 and 6·2 and optimum temperature between 50° and 55° in phosphate buffers.

Scirpus grossus, Linn., called *Kaseruk* in Sanskrit, *Kaseru* in Hindustani, *Kesur* in Bengali, *Kasra* in Marathi and *Gundatungagaddi* in Telegu, is a very large annual aquatic herb common throughout India. The tuberous root of the herb is found in the tanks and is about the size of a nutmeg. It is of black colour externally and is commonly used as a delicate article of food. With milk it forms a suitable nourishment in diarrhoea and vomiting (*vide* Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants," p. 1358). Analysis of tubers according to Dymock ("Pharmacographica Indica," Vol. III, Part VI, p. 555) is as follows:—

Fat, 0·65% ; sugar, 1·64% ; gum and carbohydrate, 5·69%, albuminous matter, 8·68% ; starch, 66·24% ; fibre, 4·51% ; ash, 2·06% ; moisture, 10·53 ; alkaloid, traces and nitrogen, 1·39%. The presence of amylase is not mentioned.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Enzyme.—A fresh supply of *Kaseru* was obtained from the Cawnpore market and its skin removed. A portion of the fruit was dried in the shade and finely powdered and another portion of the fresh fruits was crushed to extract out the juice. It was found that both the powdered starch as well as the juice showed amyolytic activity. Both can be preserved (the latter at a temperature of 4° under toluene) for a period of six months and still retain the amyolytic activity.

The juice obtained (5 c.c.) by crushing the fresh fruits was allowed to react with 2% soluble starch solution at 37° for 1 hour. Dried and powdered fruit (25 g.) was digested at 37° with 500 c.c. of water for 5 hours with occasional shaking. The clear filtrate (1 c.c.) was taken and

allowed to react with 2% starch solution (100 c.c.) at 37° for 1 hour. Also 15 g. of the dried and powdered material were triturated with dry, washed neutral sand in 500 c.c. of water for 5 hours and 1 c.c. of clear filtrate allowed to react with 100 c.c. of 2% starch solution at 37° for 1 hour. In all the three cases the action of the enzyme was stopped by pouring in an excess of Fehling's solution and boiling the reaction flasks to precipitate the copper oxide. It was filtered and estimated using Bertrand's method (Plimmer, "Practical Organic and Biochemistry", p. 228).

Treatment	Amount of CuO
Extracted juice (5 c.c.)	0.16 mg.
Dried fruit (25 g.) + 500 c.c. water digested as such (1 c.c.)	0.06
Dried fruit (25 g.) + 500 c.c. water + sand triturated (1 c.c.)	0.15

The results obtained point out the presence of amylase in the fruit. The enzyme comes out in the juice pressed out in fresh condition in fairly large proportions. It can also be preserved in the starch obtained by crushing dried fruits. Extraction of the enzyme from the starch is facilitated by triturating with dry sand while digesting out the same with cold water at 37°.

Separation of the Enzyme.—Powdered material (100 g.) was mixed up with 2 litres of water and 100 g. of neutral washed sand and triturated. It was left overnight at 37° with small amount of toluene to prevent fungus growth and then filtered. The enzyme was then precipitated with 2.5 times its volume of absolute alcohol and left over in the frigidaire to settle. The supernatant liquid was decanted out and the precipitate washed with 50% alcohol (1:1) and ether solution and then dried in shallow petri dishes in air. The powder was carefully scraped and weighed. Yield on starch (impure enzyme) was 1.4%. The enzyme powder was preserved in a cool place and used for further experiments.

Effect of p_{H} on the Activity of the Amylase.—Erlenmeyer flasks containing 75 c.c. of a 2% soluble starch solution (made by dissolving Schering-Kahlbaum soluble starch to make 2%) and 20 c.c. of buffer solutions of increasing p_{H} were kept in an incubator adjusted to $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$. When the reaction mixture had attained the temperature, 5 c.c. of the enzyme solution prepared fresh by dissolving known amount of enzyme powder was added. Before adding, the enzyme solution was allowed to attain the same temperature by leaving it in the incubator for an hour. The reaction was arrested by adding 40 c.c. of the mixed Fehling's solution exactly after one hour. The flasks were then boiled for 5 minutes and the precipitated oxide of

copper was estimated using Bertrand's method (*loc. cit.*). Buffer solutions were prepared according to Clark and Lubbs method and the p_n of the respective buffers was verified by electrometric measurements with quinhydrone electrode.

TABLE I.

Starch = 1.5%. Enzyme = 0.05%. Time of reaction = 1 hour.
Temp. = $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

p_n .	CuO using enzyme from fruit starch.	CuO using enzyme from juice.	p_n .	CuO using enzyme from fruit starch.	CuO using enzyme from juice.
3.4	2.33 mg.	4.66 mg.	5.4	13.04	15.84
3.6	3.26	5.59	5.8	<u>15.84</u>	<u>19.11</u>
4.2	5.12	6.54	6.2	<u>23.76</u>	<u>25.16</u>
4.5	5.12	7.43	6.7	6.54	6.06
5.1	5.59	8.06	7.0	2.10	3.16
			Control	0.93	0.93

It may be observed that the optimum p_n lies in the region of 5.8 to 6.2. Other amylases from plants are also reported (Sjoberg, *Biochem. Z.*, 1922, 133, 218, 294; 1923, 142, 274; 1923, 139, 118; to have their p_n optimum between 5 and 6. The optimum p_n of the enzyme extracted in the juice and the starch is the same.

Effect of Temperature on the Activity of Amylase.—The reactions were carried out in conical flasks containing 75 c.c. of a 2% starch solution, 20 c.c. of buffer of p_n 6.2 and at 0.05% concentration of the enzyme. The flasks were maintained at different temperatures in an air-oven regulated by a sensitive thermo-regulator to give the required temperatures.

TABLE II.

$p_n = 6.2$. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Temp.	CuO using enzyme from fruit starch.	Temp.	CuO using enzyme from fruit starch.
21.5°	15.93 mg.	50.0°	<u>35.31</u> mg.
31.0°	16.71	55.0°	<u>38.71</u>
37.0°	21.30	60.0°	33.17
40.0°	25.16	65.0°	28.17
45.0°	30.20	70.0°	10.93

The optimum temperature appears to be in the neighbourhood of 50 to 55° and the results are in harmony with the optimal temperatures for amylases obtained from other vegetable origin (Efront, *Compt. rend. Soc. biol.*, 1922, 86, 274).

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